

D8.2 – Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan

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Glossary and abbreviations	
Acronym	Meaning
AB	Advisory Board
API	Application Programming Interface
CA	Consortium Agreement
CDE	Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation
CL	Community Lead
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
ECCCH	European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage
EU	European Union
FSTP	Financial Support to Third Parties
GA	Grant Agreement
GLAM	Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot

PC	Project Coordinator
PMB	Project Management Board
PO	Project Officer
STL	Scientific and Technical Lead
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Lead

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the Quality Assurance and Risk Assessment Plan for the ARXIVE Horizon Europe project. It defines the methodology, processes, and responsibilities for ensuring consistent quality management and proactive risk mitigation across all project activities.

The framework is structured around three core components: **quality planning, quality assurance, and quality control**. Quality planning establishes project-wide standards, including policies for meetings, deliverables, publications, and shared templates. Quality assurance ensures that these standards are applied through structured reporting, defined responsibilities, and internal review procedures. Quality control focuses on continuous feedback loops, including internal reviews and input from the Advisory Board, to ensure corrective actions are effectively implemented.

Risk management is embedded throughout the project lifecycle and is based on continuous identification, assessment, and mitigation of risks. This includes the development of contingency measures to address potential deviations in implementation.

The plan is operationalised through the project governance structure, involving the Project Management Board (PMB), Work Package Leaders (WPLs), Scientific and Technical Lead (STL), and the Coordinator. It is designed to support collaboration, traceability, and timely decision-making across all Work Packages, ensuring alignment with Horizon Europe requirements for transparency, accountability, and audit readiness.

A key feature of this framework is its **adaptive and iterative nature**. The procedures and risk controls will be continuously refined throughout the project based on internal reviews, monitoring outcomes, and lessons learned. This ensures that the quality and risk management approach remains flexible and responsive to project evolution and emerging challenges.

This deliverable should be used in conjunction with D8.1 Project Management Plan and related consortium agreements. It provides a shared operational reference for all partners, ensuring consistency in implementation while supporting both strategic oversight and day-to-day project execution.

1. Introduction

This deliverable focuses on outlining the quality management approach and procedure for the ARXIVE project. In this context, information is shared in terms of Quality Planning, Responsibilities and Quality Assurance and Control. The deliverable focuses on the implementation of quality actions and decisions as well as the Change control, while mentioning the collaboration infrastructure, also detailed in D8.1. Information is also included as per templates, quality methods with respect to milestones and deliverables, including the

management of the WPs, the technical leadership and the dissemination and exploitation of the project.

1.1 Mapping Project’s Output

Purpose of this chapter is to map ARXIVE Grant Agreement (GA) commitments in terms of technical and quality assurance and risk assessment, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project’s respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1: Adherence to ARXIVE GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

Quality Assurance and Risk Management Task		Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
T8.2 Quality Control, Risk Management and DMP	The task focuses on defining and specifying the appropriate mechanisms and processes that will be established to maintain high quality. Task 8.2 takes responsibility for the project's quality process management, ensuring that project results, milestones, and deliverables undergo a quality control process prior to submission to the EC. Additionally, T8.2 deals with the identification of potential project management risks and the respective monitoring of each risk profile, defining and timely applying contingency plans. LUH will organize the activities in this task, with input from the WP leaders, encompassing the preparation of periodical risk reports, the identification of challenges, the suggestion of remedial actions and the implementation of any corrective measures, when necessary. Risk management forms a key part of this task, involving the maintenance of the project’s risk register and chairing regular risk assessment sessions during consortium meetings to ensure successful project delivery. This task also includes addressing any ethical issues reported. Moreover, Task 8.2 will deliver and maintain the project Data Management Plan (DMP) which will address relevant aspects of making data and other research outputs FAIR, adhering to the best practices in data management and data sharing. This comprehensive approach	Chapter 2 - Chapter 5	Chapter 2: Quality Management Strategy Chapter 3: Quality Methods Chapter 4: Procedures of Project Management Board Chapter 5: Risk Management

	maintains high ethical and quality standards while minimising the project's risk potential and managing its data effectively.		
Project Management Plan Deliverable			
<p><i>D8.2 Quality Assurance and Risk Management Plan</i> The plan will incorporate details on the quality assurance processes adopted within ARXIVE. It will define all processes and instruments to be used for the regular quality monitoring and risk assessment in the form of a handbook.</p>			

This mapping ensures full traceability between Grant Agreement obligations, internal quality procedures, and deliverable-level implementation. It supports audit readiness and facilitates consistent interpretation of project requirements across all Work Packages.

1.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The structure for this deliverable is the following: Chapter 2 starts with the Quality Management Strategy describing quality planning, responsibilities, assurance and control. Chapter 3 provides an overview of the Quality Methods, e.g. milestones, deliverables, work packages, and dissemination. Chapter 4 outlines the procedures of the Project Management Board (PMB), while Chapter 5 focuses on Risk Management, e.g. Risk Management Process and Methodology, identified risks (at proposal stage). In Chapter 6, we address the ethics aspects and legal compliance of the ARXIVE project. Chapter 7 concludes this deliverable and in Chapter 8, we will indicate relevant References for this deliverable.

The structure of this deliverable follows a logic of progressive detailing, starting from general governance principles and moving towards operational procedures and risk handling mechanisms. This ensures both strategic alignment and practical applicability of the defined quality and risk management framework.

Overall, this deliverable establishes a robust, transparent, and auditable framework that supports high-quality project execution and ensures compliance with Horizon Europe standards throughout the ARXIVE lifecycle.

2. Quality Management Strategy

Quality is the degree to which the project results fulfil the project's requirements. In order to fulfil and exceed the project requirements, a Quality Management Strategy has been defined within the ARXIVE project through three key processes, namely Quality Planning, Quality Assurance and Quality Control. These three processes are connected and interact in order to guarantee efficient and high-quality work.

2.1 Quality Planning

Quality Planning aims to define the outcomes targeted within the project as well as about outlining criteria, assessment methods and partners' responsibilities to ensure a high-level quality of the project results. It aims to enable agreement and a common understanding among the consortium members on the quality expectations and the tools and means by which to achieve and assess

the quality defined for the varied project results. Moreover, it serves the management in communicating and controlling the standards laid down for the purpose of quality assurance within the framework of the whole duration and implementation of the project.

2.2 Quality Responsibilities

Effective coordination, communication and collaboration are central for the successful implementation of the project. The general structures set up for these areas of activity are detailed in D8.1 Project Management Plan and while everyone in the consortium is responsible to deliver high-quality project results, there are various project roles along with a specific quality assurance responsibility. Aside from the personal responsibility of each project member, the WPLs represent the first instance of quality assurance and control. It is the WPLs responsibility to define and follow up on progress and specific objectives, suggesting contingency plans and risk mitigation strategies as well as to support the PMB on the quality assurance of deliverables. As the working committee of the General Assembly, the PMB is also responsible for the overall assessment of the project's progress and consequently for defining a set of expectations, criteria and means that help to verify the progress of work, the quality of results and their correspondence with the overall project objectives and time scheduling. The Coordinator's team oversees the quality management on a day-to-day basis.

This process includes the following tasks:

- To ensure that project results meet the quality expectations and acceptance criteria defined within the consortium in such a way that they (e.g. deliverables) can be submitted to the European Commission (EC)
- To ensure that WPLs, STL, and CL implement quality control measures;
- To ensure internal consensus about and compliance with the rules and principles that are established for the purpose of quality assurance;
- To ensure that rules and mechanisms for problem management and conflict resolution are applied in case of potential disputes.

A number of specific roles assigned in the ARXIVE project on a more operational level also adopt responsibility in the project's quality management. In guiding and supporting partners in their community-building efforts, the Community Lead (CL) who is also the lead of WP7 Communication, Dissemination, Outreach, Business Model Innovation, and Impact Lead is responsible for the efficient and successful outreach of ARXIVE in all the relevant communities. This task involves mainly the supervision of dissemination activities as well as requirements elicitation processes so as to make sure that the goals and targets set within this project area are achieved and also met in a timely and effective fashion. Furthermore the leader of WP7 INOVA+ together with the Task Leader of T4.3 VILS are responsible for building a sustainable business model for ARXIVE.

The STL is responsible for the scientific, innovation and technical vision and direction of the project and for the monitoring of progress in these areas, including with respect to the development and integration of the innovative technology in the deployed services. As part of WP 4, the STL supervises the technical aspects of the acceleration and residency support programme in terms of WP1, WP2 and WP3. The STL provides the ARXIVE programme and the wider

innovation ecosystem with knowledge, resources and training to become more successful and sustainable.

In terms of WP8 Coordination and Project Management, the WPL ensures that legal and ethical aspects are considered.

Consisting of all WPLs, the PMB contributes to the project's quality management by ensuring that all activities are executed in accordance with the Description of Action (DoA). If needed, the PMB takes appropriate actions to adjust the activities of a WP or task and reports proposed changes to the PMB and Coordinator.

It is in particular the task of each WPL to coordinate the work in their WP. Based on an appropriate work plan initially defined by the WPLs, they monitor the work and progress of partners involved making sure that tasks are completed in a timely manner. They also identify and manage deviations from schedule and other problems that may affect other tasks and initiate, possibly with the PMB and coordinator, corrective actions. In this respect, they ensure an accurate and effective project implementation to meet targeted outcomes and objectives. They also provide assessment of achievements such as milestones and deliverables and ensure that project results meet the expected quality. Following the reporting strategy adopted in the project, they give feedback to the PMB and coordinator about the development and progress of work on a regular basis, advise on known or potential problems that require management action and propose changes in future plans.

Clear accountability across all governance levels ensures that quality and risk management responsibilities are distributed, traceable, and enforceable throughout the consortium. Effective implementation of this plan is a key enabler for achieving project objectives, ensuring high-quality outputs, timely delivery, and maximised impact of ARXIVE results.

Advisory Board

The consortium will be supported and advised by an Advisory Board (AB) of external stakeholders, consisting of selected European organisations not directly involved in the project as partners. Their valuable feedback to the technical process of the project brings many benefits for the ARXIVE project. The AB will provide additional insight and strategic advice into the development of the project and assess the effectiveness and fairness of the competitive call and of the range of services and support we offer to the citizen science projects hosted by the accelerator. The AB members will provide an external unprejudiced view advising on strategic directions of the project in terms of detailed technical goals and impact, comment on economic feasibility and achieved or missed targets, as well as exploitation and sustainability, which further enhances the visibility of the project by participating in communication and dissemination activities.

To attain high quality results within the ARXIVE project, a strong cooperation with the AB members will actively be pursued and facilitated by frequent interaction in the form of regular conference calls and feedback rounds. Selected Advisory Board members share the interest to guide, support and provide feedback to the ARXIVE consortium with advice and expertise

throughout the project duration. Through the integration of the AB, interim feedback of enormous importance regarding the overall orientation of the project outcome is expected. This supports the path towards objectives and controls the quality of the project work as well as the quality of expected outcomes.

The Coordinator will chair the AB sessions with the participation of the PMB leads and deputies as well as the Leads of the project. The methodology addressing the collaboration with the AB members is detailed in the Grant Agreement (GA) and Consortium Agreement (CA) of the project. The Coordinator is leading this process by actively engaging the consortium partners. Advisory Board interactions are planned at key project milestones and aligned with major technical and strategic developments, ensuring timely input into project evolution and decision-making processes. The Advisory Board provides non-binding strategic guidance; however, its recommendations are formally considered by the Project Management Board and integrated into project decision-making where appropriate. All Advisory Board recommendations are documented, reviewed by the PMB, and followed by a structured response indicating how inputs are addressed or integrated into project activities.

2.3 Quality Assurance

The focus of quality assurance is on the creation and monitoring of processes. Quality assurance creates and monitors project processes, which need to be performed effectively to reach the targeted outcome. This involves the establishment of Interim Management Reports, clear responsibilities and regular, clearly guided online telephone conferences and face-to-face meetings.

The aspect of quality is managed on two levels in the project. Quality assurance comprises techniques and practices that help monitor the progress of the project and ensure quality in the processes by which results are achieved. That is, this task involves looking at how outputs were achieved and evaluating activities that drive the project implementation. In practice, the focus will be on monitoring milestones and targets that largely reflect the requirements of the DoA in the following project areas:

- Effective project management
- Adoption of standards
- Data Science support Code quality (e.g. development and documentation of scripts, data research advisory or technical training, continuous integration)
- Dissemination and outreach activities (e.g. engagement level of target audiences, website and social media channels)
- Sustainability and exploitation network (esp. potential users of project outcomes, members of a potential ARXIVE Association or network)
- Deliverables (peer-review)
- Milestones

2.3.1 Actions and Decisions

Actions present specific directives and instructions for individual project members or project teams to implement the project successfully and on time. They result from plans, agreements and decisions made during meetings, telcos or via email and correspond to important deadlines described in the DoA. Meeting minutes will generally contain a list of new and ongoing actions with the following data:

- WP/task (i.e. number and possibly title)
- Responsible person (i.e. personal and beneficiary's name)
- Description of action (i.e. what is to do)
- Deadline for action (i.e. when is it expected to be done)

Decisions are official statements that are taken and approved at either the PMB or General Assembly level. They may involve adjustments in terms of work plan, schedule, budget and responsibilities. Decisions are documented in meeting minutes and communicated via email including the following references:

- WP/task (i.e. number and title)
- Responsible person (i.e. personal and beneficiary's name)
- Description of decision
- Voting details

Decisions are regarded as implemented when the issue has been solved and corrective action has been taken.

2.3.2 Change Control

This process is a relevant part of the project management to ensure an adequate administration and controlling of change proposed during the project. It describes how to request, review and approve change before implementation. Change control involves the following steps:

- Request change
- Evaluate impact
- Make a decision
- Implement change
- Close change

Two aspects related to changes will be clearly documented during the project. Changes requested and decisions made are recorded, while details of each change are also documented. Any participant in the ARXIVE project may suggest a change to the project by providing a description of the change and a justification. The coordinator will ensure that it is documented and recorded as required as well as proactively managed. Initially, the need for change will be examined and its overall effect on the project be evaluated. That is a recommendation of whether a change should eventually be carried out or not will be based on the assessment of the following aspects:

- Quantifiable cost savings and benefits
- Legal, regulatory or other unquantifiable reason for change
- Estimated costs of the change

- Impact on timescales
- Extra resources needed
- Impact on other project activities
- New risks and issues

This assessment is made by the Project Coordinator in close collaboration with the project manager. Based on their conclusions, an approved authority will consider the change request and make a decision. Authorities may differ according to the type of change to be dealt with:

- Minor changes within scope can be approved by the coordinator.
- Changes affecting the deadline of a deliverable or other project results need to be reviewed by the coordinator who will confirm the necessary revisions in alignment with the respective WPL(s) to get the project back on course.
- Changes of scope and contract revisions will require the approval of the EC.

Changes that require the approval of the EC are only to be requested by the Project Coordinator, not directly by individual partners (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: EC Notification

If the change is approved, it is planned, scheduled and executed as agreed with the relevant project members. A post-implementation review is foreseen for changes with major impact on the project. Once implemented, the person who proposed the change checks and agrees on its implementation, and it is marked as closed in the project records by the project manager and the project coordinator.

2.3.3 Collaboration Infrastructure

In order to easily share, coordinate and collaboratively work on project-related activities (e.g. WP tasks, deliverables, reports, data sets, source codes, agendas and meeting minutes as well as guidelines) and following the respective unanimous decision of all Consortium Partners, the ARXIVE consortium mainly uses a protected shared platform for storing and exchanging project-related materials among consortium partners (e.g. for non-confidential document files, presentations, videos, dissemination material, etc.), Outlook calendar for all project related activities (telcos, webinars etc.), internal SAP and ERP system of LUH (for the management of financial items and allocation of payments to the consortium), GitHub account (to make software and data available).

The project's Outlook Calendar allows ARXIVE the coordination and common scheduling of project activities (e.g. internal conference calls, reports, deliverables, workshops etc.). A general mailing list is set up by the Coordinator and project manager and it is regularly updated in order to ensure that all persons actively involved in ARXIVE receive emails from this mailing list. The general mailing list is used primarily for WP8 project management items and important updates from the Coordinator that affect all the partners. At the same time, the consortium partners can use this mailing list in order to share updates, news and collect feedback from the whole consortium. It is recommended to start the subject of project emails with the project acronym 'ARXIVE' to allow recipients to filter emails by using their email client facilities. Another recommendation is to mind the difference between addressees and cc-ed recipients. Addressees are directly concerned and should respond within the next two business days whereas the message is merely informative for those listed in cc.

2.3.4 Templates

Among the various formats in which project work is implemented in the ARXIVE project, there are three distinct document types that are provided for the following purposes (also included in the Annex):

- Documents for the EC, including deliverables, periodic reports, explanation of the use of resources and financial statements.
- PowerPoint presentations for internal and external use, e.g., for project meetings, reviews, presentations during workshops, exhibitions, conferences etc. (see Annex).
- Web-based documents for internal use: e.g. agendas, minutes, other contributions etc.

Templates for deliverables have been created in Word. These and other documents for the EC are shared within the ARXIVE Consortium. Front covers and initial pages will contain essential project information as well as document-specific details. The following pieces of content will be included:

- Project title, project acronym, Grant Agreement (GA) number, program and type of action as well as European Union (EU) emblem and project logo (in accordance with Art. 29.4). This information is for referential purposes as well as to acknowledge the receipt of funding from the EC.
- Dissemination level: This field indicates whether the document is for public use (i.e. fully open) or of confidential kind (i.e. restricted under conditions set out in the Model Grant Agreement to, for instance, consortium members, Project Officer (PO) and project reviewers) or is marked as confidential (i.e. confidential, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC).
- Due date and actual date of submission: This field shows contractual deadlines and real completion dates.
- WP/task number: This information of the relevant WP/task is for referential purpose only.
- Nature of foreground: This field indicates the type of result produced in the project and comprises examples such as report, demonstrator, pilot, prototype, websites, press & media actions, and software.
- Approval status: This field is to confirm the final status of the document at issue, indicating its acceptance by the person responsible for approval.

- Version: In this field the version of the document is indicated in a numerical fashion, while the verbal reference 'final' should be used for the submitted version.
- Number of Pages: This information is to ensure completeness in all digital formats.
- The recommended Filename structure is: ARXIVE-<WPX>-<DYY>-<Version>.<ext>
Where:
 - <WPX> Work Package or management identifier, as for example: “WP8”, “WP1”. WP0 for non- applicable/irrelevance.
 - <DYY> Deliverable as D1.1.
 - <Name of the Deliverable> text descriptor of up to 50 characters
 - <Version> One digit version identifier, as ‘v1’, next ‘v1.1’, etc.; ‘Final’ (this will be the last version delivered to EC).
 - <Ext> Extension of the file name, usually associated with the edition tool, like doc, xlsx, ppt.
- Revision history: This table will report version, date as well as name and organisation affiliation of responsible persons that have performed the respective modification.
Versioning will be kept as follows:
 - Version integers are kept for document submission to the EC. The first submission of a document to the EC will be marked as v. 1.0. If a second submission is needed, this will be v2.0 etc.
 - Version decimals (i.e. releases) will be used for communication between partners. The first draft version to be communicated within the Consortium will be vX.1, the second vX.2 etc.
- List of authors: This table displays names and organisation affiliation responsible for the document as well as making contributions to it.

Documents will generally contain the following chapters:

- Executive Summary: This chapter is usually up to two pages long and presents a condensed version of the document. This outlines the objectives and scope of the document as well as the methodology and main results in a concise and brief manner.

The subsequent main body of the document contains the following parts:

- Introduction: This chapter states the purpose and goals of the document at issue. It must extend upon and be consistent with the executive summary as well as briefly outline the structure of the subsequent document at the end.
- Core Content: These chapters form the core part of the document. It explores the subject of the document in detail, also providing valid reasons and justifications. If an evaluation is given, (1) the measures used must be explained, (2) the data sets must be presented, (3) explanations must be given, where required.
- References: This chapter comprises a list of material which has been used as a source for writing the document. References are added either at the end of each document or at the end of the relevant chapter.
- Annexes: These chapters may contain collection of supplementary material (e.g. list of tables, figures)

Finally, in order to ensure consistency and quality of documents produced by the ARXIVE consortium, attention will be paid to the following criteria:

- Headers and footers will be formatted according to template guidelines.
- Fonts, paragraphs, bullets, numbered lists etc. will be formatted in the predetermined styles.
- Captions to all tables and figures will be used.
- References should be presented in a unified way.

2.4 Quality Control

In contrast to quality assurance, quality control circumscribes techniques and practices that serve to evaluate the different output types of the project (e.g. content, technical, evaluation/validation, dissemination/valorisation, scientific publications). This task means to determine whether the project's achievements fulfil the quality requirements and represent ultimately success or failure pertaining to contractual targets. Thus, it is simultaneously also about identifying ways to eliminate causes of unsatisfactory performance. Depending on the type of project result, quality control may additionally assess project results by aspects such as innovation (has anything genuinely new been developed?) and impact (e.g. improvement and measurable increase in responsiveness to media, measurable increase in collaborations between entrepreneurs, artists, citizens etc.). The focus of quality control is on feedback and deviation management in the project. Quality control ensures that feedback: it is taken into account from internal as well as from external advisors and therefore positively influences the work towards project objectives. Risk Management is an integral element of quality control as the proactive notice of deviations from the Description of Action (DoA) allows the consortium to control the consequences or even transform those consequences to opportunities.

2.5 Quality Management Consolidation and Continuous Improvement

The Quality Management Strategy of ARXIVE establishes an integrated and iterative framework that ensures the continuous alignment of project activities with the objectives defined in the Description of Action (DoA) and the expectations of Horizon Europe. Quality Planning, Quality Assurance, and Quality Control operate as interconnected processes that collectively support both the effective implementation and the continuous improvement of project outcomes.

Quality management in ARXIVE is embedded within the broader project governance structure and is closely linked with risk management and ethical compliance processes. This integration ensures that quality is not assessed in isolation but as part of a holistic evaluation of scientific, technical, organisational, and societal performance. Deviations identified through quality control mechanisms are systematically addressed through corrective actions, change control procedures, and, where necessary, escalation to the Project Management Board (PMB).

All quality assurance activities are systematically documented through meeting minutes, interim reports, and WP-level progress records, ensuring full traceability of decisions, actions, and follow-up measures throughout the project lifecycle. The quality assurance process functions as an early-warning mechanism for deviations from planned activities, enabling timely corrective actions

before issues escalate into significant risks. Quality assurance is closely integrated with risk management and change control processes, ensuring that deviations in performance, scope, or deliverables are systematically assessed and appropriately addressed.

The consortium applies a continuous improvement approach, whereby lessons learned, feedback from internal reviews, Advisory Board input, and stakeholder engagement are systematically incorporated into project planning and execution. This ensures adaptability to emerging challenges and supports the optimisation of both processes and results throughout the project lifecycle.

Through this structured and adaptive quality framework, ARXIVE ensures transparency, accountability, and consistency in all project activities, while reinforcing compliance with Horizon Europe principles of excellence, impact, and implementation quality.

3. Quality Methods

Quality control is the responsibility of everybody involved in each project activity. The quality control task performed by the Coordinator at project level will not substitute for internal quality control used in the various partner organisations for their internal work. All partner organisations should ensure that their existing internal quality control procedures are applied to ARXIVE tasks. However, as part of their role, the Project Coordinator, the Consortium Project Manager as well as the STL and other WPLs will collaborate with the PMB and AB and will act as Project Quality Assurance Team.

3.1 Milestones

To determine when and where key quality reviews need to take place, the project plan identifies five major key milestones with relevant dependencies between work packages as listed in the following table.

Table 2: List of Milestones

Milestone No	Milestone Title	WP involved	Due Date (Month)	Means of Verification
MS 1	Successful organization of the kick-off meeting	WP8	M1	Kick-off meeting successfully organised.
MS 2	Completion of ARXIVE workflow documentation	WP8	M3	Timely delivery of detailed project handbook.
MS 3	Project branding, dissemination elements delivery	WP7	M3	Successful delivery of the branding plan.
MS 4	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan delivered	WP7	M6	Successful delivery of the dissemination and exploitation plan.
MS 5	Establishment of 10 stakeholder hubs	WP1	M12	List of established hubs, documentation outlining the process, feedback from local stakeholders.
MS 6	ARXIVE’s research and practice framework developed	WP1	M12	The developed framework, feedback from local stakeholders, and documentation outlining the

				framework's implementation process.
MS 7	Launch of the Open Calls	WP6	M12	Publication online (EC, project, ECHOES and partners websites). Webinar presentation held.
MS 8	Annotated bibliography tools prototype validated	WP2	M14	Domain expert validation survey. Also evaluate KPI 2.1, KPI 2.2, KPI 2.4.
MS 9	Semantic metadata representations aligned	WP4	M16	Data retrieval and integration from diverse repositories. Also evaluate KPI 1.1, KPI 1.5.
MS 10	Archival tools prototype validated	WP3	M16	Domain expert validation survey. Evaluate KPI 1.2, KPI 1.3 KPI 6.3, KPI 3.5, KPI 3.1, KPI 4.3.
MS 11	Narrations creation tool validated	WP3	M16	Domain expert validation survey. Also evaluate KPI 5.3, KPI 5.6, KPI 5.7.
MS 12	First end-user training workshop concluded	WP6	M26	Open call researchers and professionals have successfully completed training. Also evaluate KPI 8.1.
MS 13	Demo AI apps published	WP2, WP3	M33	Applications source code published and user interface accessible online. Also evaluate KPI 2.3, KPI 2.4.
MS 14	Integration with ECCCH achieved	WP4	M36	Tools deployed within the official ECHOES platform. Also evaluate KPI 7.1, KPI 7.2, KPI 7.3, KPI 7.4.
MS 15	Project conclusion and final review	WP8	M36	Successful completion of the project.

3.2 Deliverables

To ensure quality of deliverables, an internal review process has been defined. The main goal of this process is to establish internal feedback by partners who did not directly participate as editor to the deliverable before submitting it to the European Commission. The review process is shown and explained below.

3.2.1 Overview of Deliverables

Deliverables are important project results that are delivered to the EC. They are created throughout the project to provide the required project output and impact. In total, 52 deliverables are scheduled in the ARXIVE project. 23 of these are due between M1-M18 and 29 deliverables are due between M19-36. The assignments of deliverable author(s) and reviewer(s) are determined well in advance for at least an entire project year. Table 3 presents the expected deliverables and the partners which are responsible for reviewing the corresponding deliverable.

With reference to project deliverables: each project deliverable is assigned to one leading responsible partner. This partner takes the responsibility that the deliverable is of high quality and timely delivered. The responsible partner assures that the content of a deliverable is consistent

with the team-workings of the deliverable and that the particular objectives related to the goals of the project are met. Any issues related to deliverables, endangering the success of the WP or the project, have to be reported by the WPL immediately to the Project Management and discussed within the Coordination team, which also conducts the final quality check before submitting the deliverable via the EC portal.

One of the peer reviewers should be the WPL, since this partner should have a better understanding of the tasks and deliverables under the WP that he/she is leading. The team of the Coordinator will facilitate changes in terms of the partners proposed as first and second reviewers. Therefore the following list by order of WPs, which is planned, can be indicative and subject to timely changes upon decision of the concerned partners and the Coordinator.

The Quality Methods defined in this section establish a structured and continuous monitoring framework that integrates milestone tracking, deliverable peer review, Work Package oversight, and KPI-based validation into a single coherent process. This ensures early identification of deviations, supports evidence-based decision-making, and enables timely corrective actions through the appropriate governance levels, including the WP Leaders, Consortium Project Manager, and Project Management Board (PMB). In combination with the Advisory Board feedback and internal review procedures, this framework guarantees consistent alignment between project implementation, technical progress, and the objectives defined in the Description of Action (DoA), while reinforcing transparency, traceability, and continuous improvement across all project activities.

Table 3: Deliverables and Reviewers

Del No	Deliverable Title	WP No	Lead	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date (Month)	1st Reviewer	2nd Reviewer
D7.1	Communication and Dissemination Plan	WP7	INOVA+	R	PU	M3	LUH	OKFNDR
D8.1	Project Management Plan	WP8	LUH	R	PU	M3	FORTH	VILS
D8.2	Quality Assurance and Risk Management Plan	WP8	LUH	R	PU	M6	VILS	INOVA+
D8.6	Data Management Plan (DMP) I	WP8	LUH	DMP	SEN	M6	NLG	VILS
D5.1	Baseline Assessment of Use-Case Pilots	WP5	INOVA+	R	PU	M8	MMP	LUH
D2.1	Retro-Digitised and Audiovisual Sources Parsers I	WP2	FORTH	OTHER	PU	M9	FhG	OKFNDR
D4.1	Data Alignment Results I	WP4	OKFNDR	DATA	PU	M10	FhG	FORTH
D7.4	Cooperation Pathways with related projects and initiatives	WP7	INOVA+	R	PU	M10	LUH	OKFNDR
D1.1	Cultural Heritage Methodology and Workflow Baseline for Libraries	WP1	FORTH	R	PU	M12	LUH	OKFNDR
D1.2	Ethical and Intersectional research innovation and practice framework I	WP1	VILS	R	PU	M12	NLG	OKFNDR
D1.3	Stakeholder Hubs mapping, application and engagement	WP1	VILS	R	PU	M12	INOVA+	LUH
D1.4	Cultural Heritage Methodology and Workflow Baseline for archaeological excavations	WP1	FORTH	R	PU	M12	MMP	LUH
D2.3	Multimodal Content Analysis and Classification Framework I	WP2	FORTH	OTHER	PU	M12	FhG	LUH
D4.3	API Specification I	WP4	OKFNDR	R	PU	M12	EUT	LUH
D7.5	Exploitation and Sustainability	WP7	VILS	R	PU	M12	INOVA+	LUH
D8.3	Policy Brief I	WP8	FORTH	R	PU	M12	LUH	INOVA+
D3.1	Knowledge Infrastructure and FAIR Data Management Framework I	WP3	FhG	OTHER	PU	M14	OKFNDR	FORTH
D4.6	Data Pipelines I	WP4	OKFNDR	OTHER	PU	M15	FORTH	LUH
D4.2	Data Alignment Results II	WP4	OKFNDR	DATA	PU	M16	FhG	FORTH
D7.2	Communication and Dissemination Report I	WP7	INOVA+	R	PU	M16	LUH	VILS

D2.2	Retro-digitised and Audiovisual Sources Parsers II	WP2	FORTH	OTHER	PU	M18	FhG	OKFNDR
D2.5	Online Collaborative Bibliographies Management Platform I	WP2	FORTH	OTHER	PU	M18	OKFNDR	LUH
D3.2	Knowledge Infrastructure and FAIR Data Management Framework II	WP3	FhG	OTHER	PU	M18	OKFNDR	LUH
D3.3	Interactive Visualization and Annotation Platform I	WP3	LUH	OTHER	PU	M20	OKFNDR	FhG
D4.8	ARXIVE Application Containers I	WP4	FORTH	OTHER	PU	M20	FhG	OKFNDR
D5.3	FSTP Framework and Evaluation Report	WP5	INOVA+	R	PU	M20	LUH	VILS
D2.4	Multimodal Content Analysis and Classification Framework I	WP2	FORTH	OTHER	PU	M24	FhG	LUH
D2.6	Online Collaborative Bibliographies Management Platform II	WP2	FORTH	OTHER	PU	M24	OKFNDR	LUH
D3.5	Reporting and Content Generation Tools I	WP3	FhG	OTHER	PU	M24	OKFNDR	LUH
D4.4	API Specification II	WP4	OKFNDR	R	PU	M24	EUT	LUH
D4.7	Data Pipelines II	WP4	OKFNDR	OTHER	PU	M24	FORTH	LUH
D8.4	Policy Brief II	WP8	FORTH	R	PU	M24	VILS	LUH
D5.2	Pilot Implementation Report	WP5	MMP	DEM	PU	M26	VILS	LUH
D5.4	Training Materials Toolkit	WP5	FORTH	OTHER	PU	M26	INOVA+	LUH
D4.9	ARXIVE Application Containers II	WP4	FORTH	OTHER	PU	M27	FhG	OKFNDR
D2.8	Annotated Bibliography Authoring Assistant I	WP2	OKFNDR	OTHER	PU	M28	MMP	NLG
D7.3	Communication and Dissemination Report II	WP7	INOVA+	R	PU	M28	LUH	VILS
D2.7	Online Collaborative Bibliographies Management Platform III	WP2	FORTH	OTHER	PU	M30	OKFNDR	LUH
D3.4	Interactive Visualization and Annotation Platform II	WP3	LUH	OTHER	PU	M30	OKFNDR	FORTH
D3.6	Reporting and Content Generation Tools II	WP3	FhG	OTHER	PU	M30	LUH	OKFNDR
D3.7	Smart Archival Assistance System I	WP3	OKFNDR	OTHER	PU	M30	NLG	MMP
D6.2	Chatbot Tutor	WP6	FhG	OTHER	PU	M30	FORTH	LUH

D6.1	Toolkit and Pathways for scaling-up innovative tools	WP6	INOVA+	R	PU	M32	VILS	LUH
D2.9	Annotated Bibliography Authoring Assistant II	WP2	OKFNDR	OTHER	PU	M36	MMP	NLG
D3.8	Smart Archival Assistance System II	WP3	OKFNDR	OTHER	PU	M36	NLG	MMP
D4.5	API Specification III	WP4	OKFNDR	R	PU	M36	EUT	FhG
D4.10	ARXIVE Application Containers III	WP4	FORTH	OTHER	PU	M36	FhG	OKFNDR
D6.3	GLAM Innovation Toolkit & Success Stories	WP6	LUH	OTHER	PU	M36	INOVA+	VILS
D6.4	Impact Assessment, Results and Recommendations	WP6	VILS	R	PU	M36	LUH	INOVA+
D7.6	Strategic Business Plan and Replication Handbook	WP7	VILS	R	PU	M36	INOVA+	LUH
D8.5	Policy Round Table Recommendations	WP8	FORTH	R	PU	M36	LUH	INOVA+
D8.7	Data Management Plan (DMP) II	WP8	LUH	DMP	SEN	M36	FORTH	VILS

The following template, serving as a quality checklist, is provided by the Coordinator in order to facilitate the reviewers of the deliverables, while enhancing consistency and efficiency.

Table 4: Quality checklist for internal review

Internal Review

Mark with X the corresponding column:

Y= yes	N= no	NA = not applicable
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Name of reviewer: XXX
 Organisation: XXX
 Date: XXX

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	Comments	Author
FORMAT: Does the document ...?					
...include editors, deliverable name, version number, dissemination level, date, and status?					
... contain a license (in case of public deliverables)?					
... include the names of contributors and reviewers?					
... contain a version table?					
... contain an updated table of contents?					
... contain a list of figures?					
... contain a list of tables?					
... contain a list of terms and abbreviations?					
... contain an Executive Summary?					
... contain a Conclusions chapter?					
... contain a List of References (Bibliography) in the appropriate format?					
... use the fonts and chapters defined in the official template?					
... use correct spelling and grammar?					
... conform to guidelines regarding Annexes (inclusion of complementary information)					

... present consistency along the whole document in terms of English quality/style? (to avoid accidental usage of copy & paste text)					
About the content...					
Is the deliverable content correctly written?					
Is the overall style of the deliverable correctly organized and presented in a logical order?					
Is the Executive Summary self-contained, following the guidelines and does it include the main conclusions of the document?					
Is the body of the deliverable (technique, methodology results, discussion) well enough explained?					
Are the contents of the document treated with the required depth?					
Does the document need additional sections to be considered complete?					
Are there any sections in the document that should be removed?					
Are all references in the document included in the references chapter?					
Have you noticed any text in the document not well referenced? (copy and paste of text/picture without including the reference in the reference list)					
Are all images and illustrations easy to see?					
Are all roles, personas or committees fully mentioned?					

SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENTS

PAGE	CHAPTER	SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENT

CONCLUSION

Mark with X the corresponding line.

<input type="checkbox"/>	Document accepted; no changes required.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Document accepted; changes required.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Document not accepted; it must be reviewed after changes are implemented.

REMARKS FOR THE DELIVERABLES OWNER

3.2.2 Production, Review Process and Assessment of Deliverables

A Review Process involving each partner and selected reviewers is adopted within the Consortium to ensure the quality of deliverables of all types (Report, Pilot Demonstrator, Data Sets, DMP or Other) and the objectives of the project and to adhere to formal requirements established in the Grant Agreement (GA) and Consortium Agreement (CA). The review process ensures that publications and deliverables comply with the IPR of the partners. For external publications as well as for project deliverables, the review process will involve all Consortium partners and requires the approval of the Project Quality Assurance Team.

Project documentation will be reviewed against the following criteria regarding form as well as content of the document:

1. Format of the document according to the document templates.
2. Identification and correction of typing mistakes, etc.
3. Check of consistency:
 - a. with the overall scope of the document (e.g. it contains the right information, avoiding unnecessary information, etc.)
 - b. with previous relevant documentation (e.g. no redundancy with other documents, etc.).

Technical aspects of the documentation will be reviewed also by the STL in order to ensure that the document meets the technical goals of the project, and that all technical information is advancing the current state of the art and the recent technological research level.

The procedures and timeline for the review project documentation are described hereafter:

- The partner responsible for preparing the deliverable drafts a Table of Contents (ToC), assigns tasks to all involved partners and sets the respective deadlines (considering also time needed for quality review).
- Involved partners provide their feedback within the deadlines and the responsible partner prepares the first draft of the document.
- This draft is sent to the relevant internal reviewers for comments and improvements/additions. The feedback period for internal reviewers should last at least ten working days. Actionable and reasonable feedback is sent directly to the responsible partner who revises the document and prepares the semi-final version.
- The partner responsible for preparing the deliverable then improves the document based on received comments. If necessary (i.e. if there are too many comments on the first round), another round of comments from the internal reviewers takes place.
- The partner responsible addresses them appropriately and prepares the final version of the document, which is sent to the Project Coordination Team (at least five days before the final deadline).

- The Project Coordination Team then submits the deliverable to the EC, the latest by the indicated deadline.

Each deliverable will be created through a similar process. The following figure presents the optimal phases and timeframes for the timely and effective production of deliverables:

Figure 2: Deliverable Production Process

Firstly, the main author(s) of a deliverable are assigned in agreement with the WPL responsible for the final approval of the deliverable. Then the structure of a deliverable and the task allocation of partners involved are discussed and confirmed with the WP leader. Those assigned to contribute will focus on providing appropriate content to the partner responsible for writing the deliverable. Based on the received input, the author(s) will prepare a final draft of the deliverable and will circulate it to the relevant peer-reviewers for feedback. If appropriate (e.g. if special expertise is needed), other partners who are not assigned as reviewers can be tagged in relevant sections for review. The review period for the reviewers takes two weeks. Based on received comments, the responsible partner will have a period of one week to undertake all necessary improvements and changes in the document and prepare a final version (if the deliverable type allows in Word and PDF format) to be sent for review and approval to the Project Coordination Team. When officially approved, the coordinator submits the final PDF version to the EC and, unless it is of confidential nature, makes the deliverable publicly available on the project's website.

The progress of deliverables is regularly checked and discussed with the WPL and within the consortium. This process allows the main author(s) to communicate problems and delays that need to be addressed for the successful completion of the deliverable and that may require appropriate intervention through the WPL. Any need to replan and reschedule work should be handled in agreement with the coordinator as outlined in Chapters 2.3.2 and 5. The coordinator informs the PO accordingly if encountering more than a one-month delay and provides feedback from the partners involved in the WP and deliverable at issue. In order to assess completeness, consistency and quality, a quality assessment occurs in terms of the review. Therefore, an internal review checklist was sent to the consortium which provides guidance for the quality assessment.

A clearly structured review process has been defined by the Project Coordination Team and approved by the consortium. This process is based on minimal rules which are implemented in cooperation between the main author(s), WPL and coordinator. Each deliverable will have at least two reviewers. One can, of course, choose more reviewers if one thinks it is suitable. The peer reviewer(s) should be chosen from an organisation other than the one(s) responsible for the deliverable.

During the process of drafting, the main author(s) will be responsible for checking the quality of the deliverable as it progresses (according to the same indicators in the table below). Reviewers will be asked to comment on the deliverable draft and undertake an overall assessment by evaluating the deliverable against the DoA as well as by evaluating the general quality of the deliverable. The main author(s) will also evaluate the final draft of each deliverable in terms of content and quality, while the coordinator will additionally perform a final review (especially in terms of language and style) before the deliverable is submitted to the EC. Table 5 provides a list of indicators that reviewers, WPL and Coordinator will use to assess the quality of each deliverable.

Table 5: Deliverable Quality Indicators

Quality Indicators	Reference
Deliverables' results are fully compliant with the Grant Agreement	ARXIVE DoA
Deliverables' results are compatible and contribute to the project objectives	ARXIVE DoA
Deliverables fully document relevant work carried out in the corresponding WP/task	ARXIVE DoA, project meetings
Templates are used as provided by the coordinator and as outlined within D8.1 Project Management Plan	ARXIVE DoA, D8.1
Deliverables are clear and readable	Editing in terms of content, language, formal structure and presentation of contents
Deliverables are complete	Checking for missing parts, non-existent references, topics not covered and unclear arguments
Deliverables are useful for the target reader	ARXIVE DoA, Project Dissemination Plan
Deliverables are submitted on time, without any delays	ARXIVE DoA
Version history is clear and well-documented	Version numbers are explicitly mentioned in the document

In terms of issue reporting and escalation procedure, the Project Coordination Team updates the consortium as per the upcoming deliverables one year in advance. During the monthly project management telcos, which are chaired and led by the Coordinator, all WP and task leaders report to the ARXIVE consortium the progress per WP, task and deliverable. This process enables the quick identification of potential delays and the solutions oriented decision making, with the objective to ensure the timely submission of high quality deliverables. Moreover, the Project Coordination Team follow up regularly via direct emails with the partners leading and participating in each deliverable, with the objective to evaluate the progress, as well as propose and implement corrective measures if necessary (e.g. guidance, advice, mediation, other adjustments with regard to effort etc.).

Based on this list, the reviewer(s) will prepare their comments and circulate them to the authors and partners involved including the WPL and Coordinator. This process will be repeated until the deliverable's quality is considered as satisfactory. When all comments have been addressed and integrated, the final version will be officially approved by the Coordinator with a request for submission.

The described production and review workflow ensures a transparent, traceable, and auditable process for all ARXIVE deliverables, aligning technical quality assurance with formal governance requirements under the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement. By integrating iterative

peer review, WP-level validation, and final coordination approval, the process guarantees consistency in quality standards across all Work Packages and deliverable types. This structured approach supports timely delivery, minimises the risk of non-conformities, and ensures that all outputs meet the expected scientific, technical, and formal standards of Horizon Europe.

3.3 Work Packages

The WPL is in charge of making sure that project work is carried out according to schedule and targeted outcomes are achieved within the given timeframes. The WP progress is evaluated on the basis of the quality indicators listed in Table 6. In addition, this quality assurance and control allows to discover delays and errors as early in the project lifecycle as possible. As soon as any risk is identified, the WP leader will define a mitigation strategy as outlined in Chapter 4.

Table 6: Work Package Quality Indicators

Quality Indicators	Reference
The WP and task activities correspond to what is planned and outlined in the DoA	ARXIVE DoA
Development is consistent with results of requirements elicitations	Requirements specifications
The WP and task activities are based on a work plan	ARXIVE WP work plan
Progress is regularly documented	Monitoring reports (Periodic Reports, Annual Public Reports), internal reports (general and WP-specific telcos and minutes, etc.), deliverables
Architecture is available	Internal documents, deliverables
If necessary, a realistic risk assessment and recovery plan are provided	Internal documents

The Work Package quality monitoring framework ensures continuous alignment between operational execution and the project’s strategic objectives by linking WP-level progress tracking with risk management and governance structures. Through regular reporting, structured KPIs, and close coordination between WP Leaders, the Project Coordination Team, and the PMB, potential deviations are identified early and addressed through appropriate corrective or escalation measures. This ensures that each Work Package contributes effectively to the overall project outcomes while maintaining consistency, traceability, and compliance with the ARXIVE quality standards and Horizon Europe requirements.

3.4 Dissemination and Exploitation

Disseminating and exploiting project results is an important process to make the project known and outcomes available to the project’s stakeholder and a wider audience. It can drive the take-up and sustainability of the project's outputs in the long run. Dissemination activities as well as exploitation tasks are generally overseen by the Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation and Sustainability Lead (WP7 Lead INOVA+) who can also be consulted on how to disseminate project results successfully. Part of the basic form required for the purpose of dissemination and exploitation is the appropriate placement of logos and a clear textual reference to the project's

funding. Unless otherwise agreed with the EC or unless it is impossible, any dissemination and exploitation of project results must display the EU emblem and contain the following text in accordance with Art. 29 “Dissemination of Results”: "This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101233418." In addition, the project logo should be visibly included. Further guidance information on monitoring and evaluation of the project dissemination will be defined in the already submitted “D7.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan”.

In terms of Exploitation of the project’s results, at an initial stage the process pertaining to intellectual property rights (IPR) was unanimously agreed upon at the CA. Each Party shall implement its tasks in accordance with the Consortium Plan and shall bear sole responsibility for ensuring that its acts within the Project do not knowingly infringe third party property rights. The intended introduction of Intellectual Property (including, but not limited to Software) under Controlled License Terms in the Project requires the approval of the Project Management Board to implement such introduction into the Consortium Plan. Moreover, WP7 on Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation and Sustainability Lead will further analyse along with all exploitation and business angles, the IPR topic in the dedicated tasks of WP8 Project Management. The update and sustainability of the project’s output is further ensured within the context of WP7 with tasks (T.1 - T7.4) and deliverables (D7.1 - D7.6) focusing on research on the topic of exploitation, e.g. on sustainable business models and sustainability strategy, commercialisation initiatives, action plans and socio-economic, democratic and technological impact assurance.

Dissemination and exploitation activities are continuously monitored to ensure alignment with the project’s scientific, societal, and innovation objectives, as well as compliance with Horizon Europe visibility and open science requirements. Progress in these areas is regularly reviewed through WP7 reporting, PMB oversight, and input from the Advisory Board, ensuring that communication, uptake, and exploitation pathways remain effective and targeted. This integrated approach guarantees that project results are not only widely disseminated but also strategically positioned for long-term sustainability and impact beyond the project lifetime.

3.5 Plan for Reporting Quality Control and Quality Assurance Problems

Based on Partners’ Status Reports, the further step to be undertaken is to identify the areas of non-conformity with the defined procedures. If non-conformities are identified, they should be documented in the appropriate form, and corrective actions to be applied. Any Partner identifying the necessity for corrective actions shall report to the Coordinator. In alignment with the Coordinator it will be added to the agenda of the project management telco. The General Assembly shall discuss the matter, either at regular or extraordinary meetings or through e-mails, web-conferences, etc. Proposals on corrective actions should be suggested and put for voting by General Assembly members. Decisions shall be documented in the minutes of the project management telco and the Coordinator will forward decisions to all partners involved. The PMB as a higher ranked management structure of the project is responsible for the implementation of corrective actions. Corrective actions should ensure:

- Effective handling of all complaints
- Reports of non-conformities

- Investigation of the cause of non-conformities with reference to quality system,
- Recording the results of the investigation
- Determining the corrective / preventive actions intended to eliminate the causes of the non-conformity
- Application of controls to ensure that corrective actions are taken and effective
- That information on actions taken are submitted to the partners

This structured reporting and escalation mechanism ensures that quality issues are systematically identified, transparently discussed, and effectively resolved through a documented corrective and preventive action cycle. It guarantees traceability of decisions, accountability across all governance levels, and continuous improvement of project implementation in line with ARXIVE quality standards and Horizon Europe requirements.

3.6 Quality Methods Consolidation and Integrated Monitoring Approach

The quality methods defined in this chapter establish a comprehensive and integrated framework for ensuring the effective planning, execution, and monitoring of all project activities within ARXIVE. Milestones, deliverables, work packages, dissemination activities, and reporting mechanisms are interconnected through a structured quality assurance cycle that enables continuous monitoring, evaluation, and improvement throughout the project lifecycle.

This integrated approach ensures that quality is not assessed in isolation at the level of individual outputs, but is instead continuously monitored across interdependent project dimensions, including scientific development, technical implementation, stakeholder engagement, and dissemination impact. The alignment of milestone tracking, deliverable peer review, and work package monitoring provides a coherent system for early detection of deviations and timely implementation of corrective actions.

Quality assurance and control activities are embedded within the project governance structure and are coordinated through the Project Management Board (PMB), the Coordinator, Work Package Leaders, and the Advisory Board. This multi-level governance model ensures that quality-related decisions are both operationally grounded and strategically aligned with the objectives of the Description of Action (DoA).

Overall, the ARXIVE quality methods framework ensures transparency, accountability, and traceability of all project activities, while enabling adaptive management and continuous improvement. It supports the delivery of high-quality, timely, and impactful results in full alignment with Horizon Europe principles of excellence, impact, and implementation effectiveness. The framework is continuously reinforced through risk monitoring and corrective action mechanisms, ensuring that any deviations are promptly addressed and that project performance remains aligned with planned objectives and quality standards throughout the ARXIVE lifecycle.

4. Procedures of the Project Management Board (PMB)

The Project Management Board (PMB) is the project body which shall ensure the quality and the effectiveness of the implementation of the project. It is composed of representatives of all the partners. The PMB shall satisfy itself about the effectiveness and quality of the implementation of the project, in accordance with the following:

- It shall consider any problem incurred during the implementation of the project and take decisions on how to solve these problems;
- It shall consider and approve the activities/project changes proposed by the partners during the project implementation period;
- It shall periodically review progress made by the project, based on documents submitted by Lead Beneficiaries partner;
- It shall examine the results of implementation, particularly achievement of the targets set for each project WP and the overall project indicators;
- It shall consider and approve Project Status Reports on project implementation;
- It shall be informed of any relevant comments made by the HorizonEurope Programme Management Authority (EU PO);
- It shall be responsible for arranging the common project events in coordination with the Communication Lead;
- It may propose any revision or examination of the project to make possible to hit the targets or to improve project management, including financial aspects;
- It approves major changes requested for the implementation of the project by each project partner;
- It approves and implements the risks assessment developed by each partner in the Periodical Status Reports.

The PMB will be chaired by a representative of the Coordinator, and co-chaired by the representative of the project partner hosting the meeting. At the end of the meeting minutes of the decisions taken are prepared by the Project Coordination Team with contributions of the participating partners and are circulated among the PMB members and all consortium partners. The Coordinator can initiate a written decision-making process. In this case the Coordinator shall send the draft decision to the members of the PMB and shall fix a deadline for comments and approval. Any assessment and/or decision of the PMB shall be free from bias and must not be influenced by personal interest of any of the individual members.

4.1 PMB Governance Consolidation and Decision-Making Framework

The Project Management Board (PMB) constitutes the central governance body of ARXIVE, ensuring coordinated, transparent, and evidence-based decision-making across all project dimensions. Its procedures integrate quality assurance, risk management, ethical compliance,

and change control mechanisms into a unified management framework that supports the effective implementation of the project in line with the Description of Action (DoA).

All PMB decisions are based on documented evidence provided through project reporting structures, including deliverables, milestone reviews, work package progress reports, and risk assessments. This ensures that decision-making is fully traceable, justified, and aligned with both technical progress and strategic objectives. Where necessary, PMB decisions may trigger corrective actions, reallocation of resources, or escalation to the General Assembly in accordance with the project governance structure.

The PMB operates as a dynamic coordination and oversight mechanism, ensuring that emerging issues are addressed in a timely and structured manner while maintaining consistency across work packages and project activities. Through its integration with the Coordinator, Work Package Leaders, and Advisory Board, the PMB ensures alignment between operational execution and strategic direction.

Overall, the PMB procedures guarantee transparency, accountability, and effective coordination throughout the project lifecycle, thereby supporting the successful achievement of ARXIVE's scientific, technical, and societal objectives in full compliance with Horizon Europe standards. PMB decisions are systematically translated into actionable tasks at Work Package level and followed up through structured monitoring, ensuring their effective implementation and enabling continuous feedback into the project's quality, risk, and performance management cycles.

5. Risk Management

To guarantee the achievement of the objectives of the ARXIVE project, it is essential to identify and understand the significant project risks. The continuous risk management process is based on the early identification of and the fast reaction to events that can negatively affect the ongoing work as well as the outcome of the project. The frequent meetings of the project bodies therefore serve as the main forum for risk identification. The identified risks are then analysed and graded, based on impact and probability of occurrence. Technical risks are analysed and graded, based on their probability of occurrence in order to answer the governing question: "How big is the risk and what is its impact?" Knowing how a risk impacts the project is important as several risks of the same type can be an indication of a larger problem.

The risks defined in the DoA are graded into low/medium/high risk levels (low as in low probability of occurrence and low impact, medium as in low/ high probability of occurrence and high/low severity and high as in high probability of occurrence and high severity).

The risks will be monitored on a regular basis and an updated risk table will be provided within the Periodic Reports, including a detailed classification and evaluation in the periodic public reports of the project due in M12 and M36. The Risk Assessment Plan will show how potential risks are assessed and mitigated in order to avoid any negative influence on the ARXIVE project objectives.

In addition to the above-mentioned tools and procedures, the project partners' and the coordinator's profound experience with Horizon Europe projects implies a high level of competence, expert knowledge, skills and qualifications, which further increases the quality of the project work. Furthermore, besides these hard skills, also soft skills, such as motivation, team spirit, and interpersonal interaction contribute to high quality project performance.

5.1 Risk Management Process and Methodology

This part of the project management deals with identifying, evaluating and eliminating or minimizing potential risks that may jeopardize the success of the project. While the consortium has initially described relevant project risks and how to address them in the DoA, risk management will be conducted throughout the project. It is a continuous process in which known risks will be regularly reviewed and new risks will need to be recognized so as to handle and control them adequately. Their assessment will lead to the formulation of appropriate mitigation measures that should help to prevent and overcome a risk or reduce its effects to an acceptable level. The process behind risk management can be broken down as follows:

1. Risk identification (i.e. recognise and describe risks)
2. Risk analysis (i.e. analyse likelihood and consequences of risks)
3. Risk assessment (i.e. determine magnitude/acceptability of risks for the project)
4. Risk response planning (i.e. create and execute action plan to prevent or minimise risks)
5. Risk control (i.e. monitor, track and review risks and mitigation actions)

In general, the approach and implementation of risk management is overseen by the Project Consortium (PC) in collaboration with the coordinator and project management. Risk management is specifically carried out on both the strategic and operational project levels to ensure that risks identified with the project are handled adequately. At the strategic level, risk management focuses on the WPs' contribution to the project objectives which is the responsibility of the PMB. At the operational level risk management focuses on the activities within WPs, which is the responsibility of each WPL. The following basic risk factors may apply to any level of the ARXIVE project:

- Complexity, i.e. activities may be too complex to be realised
- Scope, i.e. number of activities may be too large for partners to realise and/or manage at once
- Capacity, i.e. one or more partners may not be able to complete their tasks without other partners being able to take over.
- Reliability, i.e. project methods and strategies applied could be inappropriate to realise the intended outcomes
- Validity, i.e. outcomes may not reflect the real needs and priorities of the stakeholders
- Sustainability, i.e. project outcomes may not lead to a sustainable outcome

These factors will be detailed further in terms of: identified and quantified risks; contingency action per identified risk; monitoring mechanism; quantified threshold level; and line of action when threshold is overstepped. Mitigation measures developed by the team members involved will need to reflect the risk policy that the PMB and PC are responsible for and will be decided upon, as shown in Table 7.

Risk monitoring is a core component of the PM WP8. As such this item is discussed among all Consortium partners during each one of the monthly project management telcos, during which all WP and task leaders showcase the progress, discussion items and next steps of their respective WPs and tasks. Furthermore, risk monitoring is a constant topic in the agenda of all PMB meetings. The objective consists in timely identifying potential risk areas and timely deciding on solutions for such challenges.

Table 7: Sample Risk Methodology

Risk Factors	Risks	Actions	Decision Makers
Complexity	Activities may be too complex to realized	Review activities and scale down project ambitions	General Assembly (in agreement with PO)
Scope	Number of activities may be too large for Partners to realize and/or manage at once	Prioritize and scale down ambitions	General Assembly (in agreement with PO)
Capacity	One or more partners may not be able to complete their tasks without other partners being able to take over	Replace defaulting partners	General Assembly (in agreement with PO)
Reliability	Project methods and strategies applied could be inappropriate to realize the intended outcomes	Adjust project methods and strategies	WP Leader (in agreement with PO)
Validity	Outcomes may not reflect the real needs and priorities of the stakeholders	Adjust project activities and outputs	General Assembly (in agreement with PO)
Sustainability	Project outcomes may not lead to a sustainable outcome	Adjust project activities and outputs	General Assembly (in agreement with PO)

Including partners from several countries and with different expertise, the consortium identified a number of management and technical risks prior to the project start. In order to minimise these foreseen risks, the partners have concretised the project as much as possible and have agreed on the global project tasks. Furthermore, an elaborate project management structure has been defined in order to monitor the cooperation between the partners and identify and investigate potential as well as new emerging risks as soon as possible. The list of already known potential risks and corresponding contingency plans can be found in Table 8.

5.2 Identified Risks at the Proposal Stage

The risks included in the risks management table have been identified as critical to the success of the project by the ARXIVE Consortium at proposal stage. The respective mitigation measures are planned. Risks will be regularly monitored by the Coordinator according to a standard risk management plan implemented in WP8. The Coordinator will ensure that the appropriate proposed risk-mitigation measures will be timely taken if necessary. The general risk of timely hiring of personnel for performing the work plan, according to scientific excellence and gender balance is mitigated by the permanent staff of the vast majority of the consortium partners. Other risks (e.g. extra incurring costs or delays in the deliverables) will be managed by the General Assembly based on reports by WPLs; and are mitigated by a consortium involving highly experienced project managers and innovation teams.

Table 8: Critical Implementation Risks and Mitigation Actions

Risk No	Description of Risk	Likelihood (L) / Severity (S)	WP No	Proposed risk-mitigation Measures
R1	ECCCH dependencies not available on time	L: Medium; S: Medium	2, 3, 4	Spiral development, API abstraction (incremental progress), modularity, development stubs for unavailable ECCCH components, continued development, seamless integration
R2	Inaccurate OCR, poor-quality scans, degraded documents, rare scripts	L: High; S: Low	2	AI-based models tailored for specific languages and scripts. Manual validation steps for low-confidence results.
R3	Performance of AI tools not meeting expectations	L: Low; S: Low	2, 3	Training on diverse, high-quality datasets; Continuous user feedback, after training and reinforcement learning; Manual override capability; Regularly update models to reflect advancements in NLP and AI.
R4	Most significant bibliographic collections are subject to licensing restrictions	L: Medium; S: Low	2	Enabling users to create private collections, train AI models on user-provided data, supplements general models, ensuring robust bibliographic suggestions overcoming potential limitations of restricted sources.
R5	Low number of applications received within the open calls	L: Low; S: High	1, 5	Open Calls launched by WP5 and WP6 (C&D), promoting ARXIVE in reference communities. Dedicated activities, partners networks and collaborations with other EU/national partners ensure timely and quality applications.
R6	Major stakeholders involved in CH are not engaging with the project	L: Medium; S: Low	6	Engage key stakeholders at local, national, and EU levels, e.g. ephorates, cultural administrators, policy bodies, aligning with mandates and tailoring collaboration frameworks to ensure representation across governance tiers.
R7	The volume of data to be persisted exceeds available resources	L: Medium; S: Medium	3	Utilize cloud platforms, e.g. EOSC, to optimise local infra-structure handling storage demands of large digital twin components effectively.
R8	Tools are not validated by end-users	L: Medium; S: Low	1, 2, 3	Fail early via iterative testing cycles with active user involvement, feedback-driven refinements, tailored training, aligning tools with end-users.
R9	Delayed responses from partner prevents timely delivery of project	L: Low; S: Medium	7	Prompt Coordinator intervention, escalating to Project Management Office for corrective actions, e.g. reassigning responsibilities.
R10	Key-staff cannot be recruited on time	L: Low; S: High	ALL	Key staff is already hired; additional recruitment focuses on non-key tasks, adjusting work schedules and internal resources addressing issues.

R11	Communication and engagement failures	L: Low; S: Medium	6	Experienced communication partners prioritise impactful communication, with successful track record in EC-funded projects. Continuous monitoring to timely adjust.
R12	Lack of external user uptake Medium/High	L: Medium; S: High	6	Intense engagement with target audiences, employed diverse formats and channels, including scouting and nurturing user uptake, innovation management in WP5 and WP7.
R13	Difficulty to attract attendees to events	L: Medium; S: High	6	Event planning, incl. registration monitoring, targeted recruitment, promotion leveraging networks, co-locating events boosting participation and reducing costs.
R14	Poor Exploitation	L: Low; S: Low	6	Regular analysis of exploitation roadmap, targeting communities' and markets, related needs, enhancing exploitation actions
R15	Business Plan and exploitation roadmap show low market potential	L: Low; S: Low	6	Address business road to market, incl. societal benefits with strong interaction with end users; collecting inputs from partners and relevant end-users; use of several data sources.

Risk management in ARXIVE is established as a continuous and iterative governance process rather than a one-off planning activity. In addition to regular monitoring through monthly project coordination teleconferences and Project Management Board (PMB) meetings, the consortium will maintain a **living risk register** throughout the entire project duration. This register will be centrally managed under WP8 and will include, for each risk, its classification, assigned ownership, mitigation measures, implementation status, and residual risk assessment.

All identified risks will be systematically reviewed and updated at least on a quarterly basis, as well as in preparation for each reporting period (M12, M24, M36). This ensures that the risk profile of the project remains accurate, transparent, and aligned with evolving technical, organisational, and external conditions. Particular attention will be given to residual risks, i.e. risks that remain after mitigation measures have been applied, in order to ensure that any remaining exposure is explicitly acknowledged and actively managed.

Where mitigation measures are found to be insufficient or where a risk escalates in likelihood or severity, a structured escalation procedure will be activated. Depending on the level of severity, risks will be addressed either at WP level (operational risks), escalated to the PMB (cross-WP or medium-to-high risks), or referred to the General Assembly for strategic decision-making in cases of high impact or persistent risks. Corrective actions may include reallocation of resources, adaptation of technical approaches, modification of workflows, or revision of implementation timelines.

This escalation mechanism ensures that decision-making remains both timely and proportionate to the severity of identified risks. Furthermore, it enables adaptive project governance, allowing

the consortium to respond effectively to unforeseen challenges while maintaining alignment with project objectives and contractual obligations.

Overall, the ARXIVE risk management framework is designed as an adaptive governance instrument that evolves throughout the project lifecycle. It ensures that risk identification, assessment, and mitigation are not static activities but are continuously informed by implementation experience, stakeholder feedback, and external developments. Through its integration with quality assurance processes, project governance structures, and reporting obligations, the framework strengthens the consortium's capacity to anticipate uncertainties, respond effectively to deviations, and safeguard the achievement of project objectives in line with Horizon Europe requirements.

6. Legal and Ethical Compliance

Ethics constitutes a foundational pillar of ARXIVE's quality assurance and risk management framework. The ARXIVE consortium recognises that quality assurance mechanisms must extend beyond technical and administrative dimensions to encompass ethical compliance of project activities, outputs, and impacts on beneficiaries and stakeholders. While dedicated chapters in D8.1 cover gender equality, legal compliance, social responsibility, research integrity, and ethical governance this section focuses specifically on ethics compliance mechanisms embedded in quality processes.

ARXIVE adheres to Horizon Europe ethical standards, GDPR, the EU AI Act, intellectual property regulations, and cultural heritage protection laws. WP8 (led by LUH) oversees ethics compliance, and T8.3 - Gender, Ethical, Legal, Social and Cultural Accountability and Compliance (GELSCAC, led by VILS) provides continuous monitoring. Key ethics compliance areas include: (i) data protection and privacy; (ii) research integrity; (iii) informed consent and participant protection; (iii) intellectual property rights and licensing; (iv) cultural heritage respect and community engagement; (v) responsible innovation practices, (vi) gender equality and inclusive participation.

6.1 Ethical Risks and Mitigation

The following ethical risks are to be considered alongside technical and managerial risks.

Key ethical risks identified include:

- Potential misuse of project tools causing harm or discrimination
- Inadequate informed consent or privacy protection in research
- Inappropriate representation of Cultural Heritage or minority communities
- Unequal access based on gender, nationality, or protected characteristics
- Failure to ensure equitable benefit-sharing
- Conflicts of interest
- Lack of transparency

Risk mitigation measures include:

- Early stakeholder engagement
- Inclusive decision-making processes

- Transparent documentation of methodologies and funding
- Data protection and privacy practices
- Regular ethics audits.

All project partners commit to promptly reporting ethical concerns through established confidential procedures.

6.2 Ethics in Deliverables and Quality Review

Every deliverable is subject to an ethics and legal compliance review as part of the quality assurance procedure, as outlined in D8.1 Project Management Plan in Chapter 7. Reviewers assess whether deliverables (i) respect ethical principles, (ii) ensure research integrity, (iii) include appropriate disclaimers and attribution, (iv) comply with data protection and intellectual property regulations, (v) assess gender inclusivity and accessibility and (vi) demonstrate cultural sensitivity. Deliverables incorporating cultural heritage aspects must document provenance, respect community protocols, and avoid perpetuating colonial or exploitative approaches. All project reports include a compliance statement confirming adherence to ethical and legal standards.

6.3 Capacity Building and Training

Ethics training and resources are provided to all consortium members based on the needs, covering legal obligations, data protection, research integrity, and cultural sensitivity and guidance might include addressing challenges in fieldwork, participatory research, and community engagement. Training materials and ethics checklists are maintained in the project's internal repository for continuous reference and improvement.

6.4 Governance and Accountability

Ethics governance is embedded in project management structures. Ethical and legal compliance is monitored continuously; the GELSCAC leader (VILS) constantly monitors the ethics status, including risks identified, mitigation measures, corrective actions implemented, and lessons learned; if necessary, deviations trigger escalation to the PMB. Regarding project decisions which would pose potential ethical implications, they are reviewed by the PMB in consultation with ethics experts. In case that non-compliance incidents are documented, they are investigated promptly and reported to the European Commission as and if required. ARXIVE ensures that research excellence and ethical integrity are mutually reinforcing, strengthening both project outcomes and stakeholder trust. For further reference, detailed guidance on broader ethical and intersectional research frameworks in Cultural Heritage is provided on D1.2.

6.5 Ethics Compliance Synthesis and Continuous Assurance

Ethical and legal compliance in ARXIVE is implemented as a continuous and adaptive assurance process integrated across all work packages, rather than as a standalone or one-time evaluation activity. The ethical framework presented in this chapter operates in close coordination with the

project's quality assurance and risk management systems, ensuring that ethical considerations are systematically embedded in planning, implementation, and dissemination activities.

Compliance is monitored on an ongoing basis through WP8 governance structures and the dedicated GELSCAC mechanism, ensuring that ethical risks are not only identified and mitigated, but also tracked over time through documented follow-up actions and residual risk assessment. This includes the continuous evaluation of ethical dimensions in relation to emerging technical developments, stakeholder engagement activities, and data-driven processes. T8.3 (GELSCAC) operates as a transversal compliance mechanism embedded in WP8, ensuring continuous monitoring of gender, ethical, legal, social and cultural dimensions across all project activities. It provides structured input to quality assurance and risk management processes, including deliverable reviews, stakeholder engagement activities, and data governance practices. Its outputs feed into the PMB decision-making process where required, particularly in cases involving ethical sensitivity or compliance risks.

Where ethical risks or non-compliance issues are identified, structured escalation procedures are applied, ensuring timely intervention at WP, PMB, or General Assembly level depending on severity. Corrective actions are implemented without delay and are documented in the project's internal reporting system to ensure full traceability and accountability. Through this integrated approach, ARXIVE ensures that ethical compliance is not limited to regulatory adherence, but actively contributes to research quality, societal trust, and responsible innovation. This framework is fully aligned with Horizon Europe principles of research integrity, accountability, transparency, and respect for fundamental rights.

Overall, ethical and legal compliance in ARXIVE is embedded as a cross-cutting and continuously monitored dimension of project governance, fully integrated with quality assurance and risk management processes. This ensures that ethical considerations are systematically reflected in all project activities, from design and implementation to dissemination and exploitation. The combination of preventive safeguards, ongoing monitoring, and structured escalation procedures guarantees full traceability of ethical decision-making and reinforces accountability across the consortium. In doing so, ARXIVE ensures that compliance with ethical and legal standards is not only a regulatory requirement, but a core enabler of responsible research, societal trust, and high-quality project outcomes in line with Horizon Europe principles.

7. Conclusion and Next Actions

D8.2 Quality Assurance and Risk Assessment Plan focuses on the quality management approach and procedure for the ARXIVE project, addressing aspects of Quality Planning, Responsibilities and Quality Assurance and Control. The interrelated quality processes – planning, assurance and control – impact the project work from its start to its end. The project aims at obtaining a high degree of quality, where outcomes are achieved in terms of the effectiveness and efficiency of working practices, as well as products and standards of project deliverables and outputs. This plan seeks to establish the procedures and standards to be employed in the project, and to allocate responsibility for ensuring that these procedures and standards are followed. D8.2 includes input on the implementation of quality actions and decisions as well as the change control, quality methods with respect to milestones and deliverables, including the management

of the WPs, the technical leadership and the dissemination of the project. With regards to risk management, D8.2 outlines the risk management process and methodology to be used in ARXIVE. It further includes input on identified risks at the proposal stage.

Consequently D8.2 Quality Assurance and Risk Assessment Plan serves as a guide for the quality and risk management already implemented since the start of the project. The respective task is open and ongoing throughout the duration of the project. When and if appropriate, e.g. in exceptional cases, the Quality Assurance and Risk Assessment Plan outlined in D8.2 will be adapted to best serve the appropriate project management of the project. Furthermore, the lessons learned throughout the project will be used to further refine or adapt the foreseen methodology, aiming thus to guarantee that the project will be managed appropriately and all potential risk items are timely and proactively foreseen and addressed.

The Project Quality Assurance Team (Coordinator and Leads) monitor that the above-described processes are fulfilled. In case of any deviations to the planned work the respective WPL in alignment with the Project Coordination Team is in charge of taking necessary mitigation measures. The plan is effective throughout the lifetime of the project, but is open to revision if necessary. Responsibilities for quality planning, assurance and control are shared between all partners, which allow various views on quality issues in order to reach the optimal outcome.

7.1 Final Remarks and Operational Continuity

D8.2 establishes a structured, integrated, and operationally applicable framework for quality assurance and risk management within ARXIVE, ensuring that all processes are aligned with the project's objectives, governance structure, and Horizon Europe requirements. The procedures defined in this deliverable are not static but are designed to function as a living framework that evolves in response to project developments, stakeholder feedback, and lessons learned during implementation.

The continuous application of quality and risk management measures ensures that deviations can be identified early and addressed through appropriate corrective actions, while also supporting informed decision-making at both operational and strategic levels. This dynamic approach strengthens the overall resilience of the project and contributes to maintaining high standards of scientific, technical, and organisational performance.

Throughout the project lifecycle, the Quality Assurance and Risk Management framework will be regularly reviewed and, where necessary, refined to ensure ongoing relevance and effectiveness. This iterative approach ensures that ARXIVE remains adaptive, transparent, and aligned with best practices in European research and innovation project management. In operational terms, the implementation of this framework will be ensured through continuous coordination between the Coordinator, Work Package Leaders, and the Project Management Board, with structured reporting cycles feeding into periodic reviews and formal reporting obligations. This guarantees that quality assurance and risk management activities are not only defined at strategic level but are consistently applied in day-to-day project execution, ensuring full traceability and accountability across all ARXIVE activities.

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9. Annex: ARXIVE Presentation Template

Overall slide master

Cover slide

Title

Sub-title

Date, Place

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Presentation slide

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Closing slide

10. Consortium

